

Prosthetic Rehabilitation of a Rare Case of Maxillary Osteomyelitis With A Closed Hollow Obturator Using lost Wax-bolus Technique

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Abstract

In this case report, our main goal was to preserve the patient's remaining teeth and providing a prosthesis during the healing period which would serve for both mastication and healing. Maxillary teeth were lost due to osteomyelitis, leaving unhealed necrotic area. Use of an interim obturator with teeth on occlusal surface served the purpose of mastication. Major emphasis was given on keratinization of the soft tissues for preparation of a better foundation for placement of occlusal stress. Implant supported prosthesis was not opted for, to prevent the patient from the trauma of major surgical intervention. The interim obturator used in our case, served to fulfil the nutritional and esthetic needs of the patient.

Keywords: Mucormycosis, osteomyelitis, obturator, mastication, esthetics

Introduction

Maxillary defects, whether congenital or acquired, make patient encounter an array of physical and psychological difficulties, leading to an extremely poor quality of life. Smaller sized defect can easily be reconstructed surgically subject to favorable tissue response. Large maxillary defects are often associated with the loss of hard tissues including bone and teeth complicated with overlying soft tissue collapse.

In such situations, the prosthetic obturators help in a great extent as they not only replace the defect portion but also provide masticatory and speech functions by replacing the teeth and natural anatomical form of the missing structures.[1] The limitation of such prosthesis that is intended to replace all of the missing structures will invariably be bulky, and the added weight and volume further complicates retention of the prosthesis.

Thus the obturators are hollowed out in the defect portion to reduce its weight as a standard practice. Wu and Schaaf [2] designed different types of obturator prostheses (both solid and hollow) based on Aramany's classification and evaluated for weight reduction. They concluded that hollow obturator prostheses had significantly increased weight reduction, from 6.55% to 33.06% depending on the size of the defect.[2] Numerous processing techniques are described in the literature to fabricate the closed-hollow obturator. The processing technique discussed in this article emphasizes on incorporation of pre shaped 'wax-bolus' resulting into a single unit hollow obturator with uniform wall thickness around the hollow space ensuring the least possible weight.

Case Report

A 48-year Patient named Uzma repor-

ted to the Department of Prosthetic Dentistry, Career Dental post graduate Institute of Sciences and Hospital, Lucknow for prosthetic rehabilitation of an acquired maxillary defect secondary to osteomyelitis of jaw.

Patient gave history of a series of surgical procedures that were carried out in order to remove the necrotized and denuded hard and soft tissues of the maxilla. The patient's medical history revealed osteomyelitis of maxilla. For Radiographic examination ortho pantomogram (OPG) was prescribed, which revealed bone defect in the floor of left maxillary sinuses and hard palate, along with removal of the half maxillary alveolus.

Figure 1: Maxillectomy defect

On extra oral examination, gross asymmetry of the left side of the face was evident. Intra oral examination revealed, partially edentulous maxillary arch and the teeth present were from 11 to 17. Half of the hard palate was missing on palpation and its soft tissue surface was mobile. The buccal and labial vestibules were obliterated on the left side. [Figure 1] The mandibular arch was pa-

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rtially edentulous and teeth missing were 36,37 and 46,47 Mandibular movements were within the normal range, there was no supra eruption of teeth and tongue function was also normal. The patient presented with obvious difficulty in mastication, nasal regurgitation and poor articulation of speech. There was also an esthetic setback as the left side of the face appeared collapsed. The prosthetic difficulties one could foresee were the lack of a firm, immobile bony basal seat for denture support; absence of ridges to help in retaining a prosthesis; the absence of residual alveolar ridges to indicate the lateral tooth position during teeth arrangement, and obliteration of the labial and buccal vestibules—a condition which tends to dislodge a prosthesis. After thorough examination of the patient, treatment plan was decided.

Steps undertaken to rehabilitate acquired maxillary defect is under the following headings:

Primary Impression

In order to make the preliminary impression of the patient's maxillary arch, the oro nasal defect were first packed with gauze that was tied for easy retrieval, and then alginate impression material was used to record the impression in a modified stock tray. The impressions were then poured in type II gypsum product (Dental plaster; Kalabhai Karson, Mumbai, India) and preliminary casts were obtained.[Figure 2]

Custom Tray Fabrication

Over the maxillary cast, a custom tray was fabricated with auto-polymerizing resin material. (DPI RR Cold Cure; Dental Products of India, Mumbai, India. The custom tray was made to extend to the defect side, such that it could carry the impression material up to 5 mm into the defect area. Peripheral molding was done with green stick compound (DPI Pinnacle, Tracing Sticks Dental Products of India, Ltd) and a final impression was made with medium body elastomer (3M ESPE Express Std., Germany) to get a resultant master cast.

Figure 2:(a)Primary impression (b) Primary cast (c) Border moulding (d) Secondary impression(e) Master cast

Jaw Relations

A record base (DPI RR Cold Cure; Dental Products of India, Mumbai, India) and record rim from modeling wax (Modeling wax; Deepti Dental Products, Ratnagiri, India) was fabricated on a master cast and jaw relations was done.[Figure 3a]

Figure 3: (a) Jaw Record (b) Teeth Arrangement (c) Try-in

Try-In

Teeth arrangement was guided by lip position, nasolabial angle, lip length and longer maxillary anterior teeth were selected for adequate lip support and visibility. The final arch form and tooth position was determined by phonetics and esthetics. Their position was verified with phonetic tests that required the patient to pronounce /s/, /f/, /v/, and /th/ sounds. C-clasp was given on right maxillary first molar and pinheads were secured between right maxillary pre-molars and left maxillary canine which will aid in retention of the prosthesis. [Figure 3b] [Figure 3c]

Laboratory Steps

- After the try-in of the waxed-up palatal obturator prosthesis, free the wire assemblies by removing the surrounding acrylic resin from the record base and seal the cut portion and the borders with the baseplate wax.
- Investing, flasking and dewaxing was performed in a conventional manner.[Figure 4a]
- Three widely distributed straight lines were marked originating from the defect portion of the cast and extending on the investing plaster surface till the end. These tripod lines would act as a guide to reseat the wax-bolus in its original position during packing.[Figure 4b]
- A double thickness baseplate wax was adapted in area corresponding to future hollow space of the obturator both on the base flask and on the dewaxed plaster surface of the counter flask.
- 3 rectangular windows (3 mm × 3 mm) were cut through on the adapted wax sheet in the base flask followed by application of a petroleum jelly which acts as a separating media.
- Soften modeling wax sheets to form a wax-bolus for the filling the space between the drag and counter of the utility flask. Now position the bolus over the adapted wax sheet and close both portions of the flask under the mechanical clamp. Keep flask-clamp assembly under cold water for 10 min. Separate the flasks and smoothen out excess flush of the wax from the margins of bolus. [Figure 4c]
- Carefully remove the adapted wax sheets and from both the flasks. Mix the heat polymerizing acrylic resin to pack into the base flask. Orient the wax-bolus according to the guide-markings and press it over the packed acrylic resin till all the stops rest in original position on the cast in the base flask. [Figure 4d]
- Place acrylic resin dough in the counter flask as well and close it in approximation with the base flask to bench press it under the mechanical clamp.
- Curing cycle was performed as per the manufacturer instructions. Keep the flask-clamp assembly at room temperature after completion of curing cycle for 24 h (bench cooling) Separate the flasks to retrieve the cured prosthesis. [Figure 4e] The wax-bolus enclosed within the acrylic resin was flushed off by forcefully injecting hot water with a syringe through the openings (corresponding to the stops) while some portion of wax partially got melted and came out of the resin-obturator through the openings during curing cycle.
- Seal the three holes with auto-polymerizing acrylic resin as described by Patil and Patil. [3] [Figure 4f]

Figure 4: (a) Flasking of waxed-up prosthesis (b) Modeling wax sheet adapted on defect area on base and Wax-bolus has taken shape of hollow space between two adapted sheets (c) Shaped wax-bolus. (d) Wax-bolus seated in initial position over acrylic resin (e) & (f) Cured prosthesis

Delivery of The Finished Hollow Bulb Obturator

On delivery of the finished interim obturator, careful occlusal adjustments were performed to ensure that dislodging interferences were minimized wherever possible. The extensions of the prosthesis into the oro-nasal communications were checked and adjusted to eliminate any soft tissue irritation in that area.

The patient was trained to remove and insert the prosthesis and post insertion instructions were given. The patient was recalled after 24 hours for a follow-up. Recall visits were scheduled after 1 week, 1, 3, and 6 months, and 1 year with satisfactory results. The patient adapted well to her prosthesis and not only perceived that her speech had returned to near normal, but she reported good masticatory ability and was satisfied with the cosmetic outcome. The prosthesis showed satisfactory retention and esthetics. [Figure 5]

Figure 5: (a) floating hollow obturator with sealed holes. (b) Obturator in place intra orally

Discussion

This case report highlighted a non-invasive prosthodontic management of the defect while it was yet to be epithelized. The prosthesis aided in formation of a keratinized surface, which helped in bearing occlusal stress and improved aesthetics. [4]

Several techniques and materials have been described previously to fabricate a lightweight, hollow obturator. [5-27] Grinding out the interior of the bulb, [6] fastening the lid to the superior border, [7] incorporation of the materials like sugar [6] and ice [8] during packing are some of the methods to create the hollow prostheses. Separate processing of two halves followed by joining them with an auto polymerizing resin. [9,10] or two step processing technique, using preformed plastic shapes, [11] plaster matrix, [12] resin shim, [13] and a polyurethane foam [14] are also described in the literature. Additional techniques with the use of combinations of impressions, casts and multiple laboratory procedures rendered them time-consuming

and limited in application. The uniform wall thickness of a hollow prosthesis ensures the least possible weight. Worley and Kniejski [15] described a method for the fabrication of a closed hollow obturator while controlling the thickness of the hollow portion. However, the asbestos used by them is unacceptable by current health and safety.

The technique described in this article is superior to all other techniques previously described in two ways:

1. It gives the complete prosthesis as a single unit in a heat cured acrylic resin and
2. Size and shape of the hollow space achieved allow uniform wall thickness for closed hollow obturator. One step processing in heat cured resin as a single unit with predictable internal dimension of the hollow space is the characteristic feature of this technique.

Some of the issues regarding the technique should be carefully handled to achieve the best possible results like: reliable seating wax-bolus in polymerizing resin during packing, bench-polymerization of 24 h immediately after packing is compulsory to avoid wax-bolus distortion in curing process, wax-bolus is kept in ice-cold water to harden it to prevent distortion by packing pressure.

Definitive prosthodontic treatment should only be considered once the healing is complete. The use of prosthesis supported on osseointegrated dental implants is also a viable treatment option, however availability of sufficient bone, keratinized mucosa, and feasibility of distraction osteogenesis and the psychological trauma of another surgical procedure are the major factors limiting this approach. In this case, the use of an interim obturator assisted in making fibrous changes to the necrotic tissue.

In the above presented cases, our aim was to eliminate the communication of the oral and nasal cavity by means of an obturator prosthesis, providing adequate functions of chewing, swallowing, and speech, as well as acceptable esthetic appearance. In the construction of an interim obturator, the design of the alveolar area is crucial because, during speech, the tongue comes into contact with sections of teeth, alveolar ridge and hard palate. The palatal contour of the prosthesis was also waxed to achieve good phonetics. The idea of fabricating a closed-hollow obturator design was to reduce the weight by creating an air space. Use of teeth on the occlusal surface helped in fulfilment of oral function and nutritional requirement of the patient. However, the limitation was slow healing during follow-up visits.

Long-term follow-up and evaluation with an eye to the possibility of lesion recurrence is a part of the crucial contribution by the prosthodontist. [28]

Conclusion

The benefits of such hollow bulb interim prosthesis was that the technique followed were noninvasive, economical, tissue tolerant, esthetic to the patient, comfortable to use, easy to fabricate and clean, and with reported improvements in both speech and mastication with its use. The weight of the obturator can act as a dislocating force; hence the prosthesis should be as light as possible.

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